

Use of Test Technology in Improving Literacy of High School Students

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Abstract:

The article focuses on the Uzbek language, implementation of the law "On the State Language", shortcomings in this regard, issues of literacy, improving students' literacy, research conducted in this regard, successes achieved, the impact of the family on improving literacy, future tasks related to the quality teaching of the mother tongue, increasing attention to the issue of literacy, and issues related to the training of highly qualified personnel in this field will be covered.

In the course of our research, we will think about the advantages of using test technology in improving the literacy of high school students. It is explained that the cultural level and responsibilities of parents are important in developing the student's spirituality, increasing the level of knowledge and literacy.

Keywords: literacy, conjunctions, prepositions, adverbs, syntactic analysis

According to the basic requirements of language education, the student should independently think creatively, observe, find commonalities, identify differences, compare, classify, draw conclusions while completing exercises and tasks in the textbook in order to acquire the knowledge, skills and skills set on the subject. should be able to open the relationship and apply it in practice. The use of interactive methods for the formation of the competence of independent work and creative thinking in improving students' literacy is very effective. In this case, all students are involved in the lesson process, and the teacher determines to what extent they have mastered the subject based on their participation in the process of completing the assignment. One such interactive method is the "**Reverse Test**" method.

The word "test" is an English word that means to try and check. A short problem, task, example, puzzle, plot picture or form used to check a person's mental growth, mentality, ability, willpower and other characteristics is called a test.¹

Test methods expensive of experience scientific to the level of the inspector skill and interest, collected of information objectivity and them scientific analysis do it to know depends. In the test question is given and his the answer is in variant form will be of the question the answer from options one choose through is determined .

"Reverse test" method and the test answer is in variant form given and that's it to options based on question is made. This is the method to the answer relatively how thoughts that there is shows and of the student quickness increases. Below the topic of the compound sentence from the " Reverse test" method used without appropriation showing will be passed .

Conjunctive sentence syntax separately one structural-semantic is unity. Two or from him more than simple talk content, grammar and tone in terms of from the merger a structured sentence is called a compound sentence. The compound sentence is simple out of the question to the structure and thought to express character according to differs .²

In a simple sentence one have and section unit participation if, in a compound sentence two and from him more than have and section unit participates. M: *The door slowly opened, Kalandarov's face was seen* First in the sentence *the door* has, *opened* section Second in the sentence while *face* has, *seen* section In the compound sentence simple sentences mutually binders, downloads and verb forms and tone through is connected. Content relationship and binder of means to be used according to joint sentences three different will be : bound joint sentences followed joint sentences and without a binder joint words³

Reverse test method :

1.?

A) Mashrab that's it good he knows, his friend him does not deceive

B) Either of the earth power no, yes the seed is good it's not

C) Who is drunk help if he wants, that's it gore around will be

D) In this house neither From Ashir, no From happiness a tree there is was

(question options as follows to be possible)

1. A connected clause is given line define

2. Of the following answers which in one No conjunction given ?

3. Separate parts connector using connected joint talk define

4. The following of answers which in one that's it to the mold suitable coming given a conjunction ?

5. The following of answers which in one that's it to the mold suitable coming given a conjunction ?

Reverse test method one to understanding wider in the approach, less time inside big to the result to reach help gives

First to the question right answer **B** option .

¹ Uzbekistan national encyclopedia . 2000-2005

²Current Uzbek literary language T.: Teacher, 1987. p. 159

³ Fundamentals of compound sentence syntax T .: Science, 1985.

Connected parts of speech equal to conjunctions, -u, -yu, -da loadings and if words using is connected. **A** is the answer joint parts of speech mutually – **ki** particle with connected came -ki loading followed parts of a compound sentence to connect service does, therefore option A for it is not true. **C** of the answer error is also binding in the tool. In it - **sa** a must ok addition in binding participation is doing - sa a must ok suffix also followed joint talk to connect service does D to the answer stopable if so, in the answer talk as a conjunction not taken. It is a simple sentence. *This is at home neither From Ashir, no From happiness a tree there is was* This in the sentence *there is was* cut, *tree* has *at home* the word place anyway, *from Ashir* and *From happiness* words medium filler on duty is coming In the matter participation reached *neither ... nor* connector sentences not, united medium fillers to connect service by doing came One thing cut to the sign have that it was for is a simple sentence .

Second to the question right answer by itself If option **D is** taken will be The reason in answer D above talk that it is simple syntactic analysis to do through we explained. No conjunction given answer option D right will come The rest option of words all of them compound sentence.

Third to the question alternative answer **B** is the answer .

Connectors in the sentence to the task according to two type divided by : equal binders and follower binders. Equal conjunctions while own in turn

1. Attachment connector;
2. Opposite connector;
3. Separation connector;
4. Denial connector

such as to groups is divided .⁴

Things, events - events from others separate or their sometimes happens

to be show for service doer either, or, or ..., either, or, sometimes such as words separation connectors is ⁵considered *Oh of the earth power no, yes the seed is good it's not* joint in the sentence **or ...**, **or** separation connector participation reached This there are two conjunctions simple out of the question organize found being the first simple talk the owner *power*, section *no* words Second talk the owner while *seed, good it's not* section

The fourth **C** to the question answer right will come

Followed joint sentences equal to didn't happen from components - head and follow from sentences organize finds The main sentence is content and to the structure according to much independently made up being, by the adverbial clause explained. Content the sentence being explained is the main clause, the content of the main clause and the sentence that explains it is called a subordinate clause .

follow sentences to the main clause the following tools using connects to:

⁴ C.T.: Science, 1976. p. 11

for students of the faculty of philology of pedagogical institutes, T.:

Means that come in the main clause:

a) -ki particle;

b) because of that

auxiliary devices such as

In the drawing as shown the subordinate clause is round, the preposition is square form with is expressed. *Who is drunk help if he wants, that's it gore around will be* in the sentence The first sentence is the subordinate clause, the second sentence is the main clause. The subordinate clause to the main clause - sa a must ok tool using connected. Above as shown

- sa a must ok shape addition only in a subordinate clause will come

The fifth to the question **A** answer right will come

Mashrab that's it good he knows, his friend him does not deceive. A is the answer given this in the sentence the first sentence is the introductory sentence and the second sentence is a subordinate clause. The subordinate clause is the preposition of -ki using connected is coming -ki loading is only in the preposition coming showing passed .

"Reverse test" method not only types of conjunctions in separation, perhaps to the students a lot cases difficulty birth followed joint of parts of the sentence participation according to in determining the type as well if he uses will be

Followed joint preposition in sentences section which word category with expressed strictly look person additions acceptance does And the next sentence content and to the structure from the main clause than different build up and start the sentence something piece of or the preposition as a whole explains. follow talk section person additions always acceptance to do a must it's not. Followed compound sentence components connector grammar tools follow talk section in the composition is used. Joint talk organize reached of components content and them connector tools account received without follow sentences the following to species is separated :⁶

- 1) have follow speaking conjunction;
- 2) section follow speaking conjunction;
- 3) filler follow speaking conjunction;
- 4) determiner follow speaking conjunction;
- 5) case follow speaking compound sentence

Followed joint talk above types separate for mostly in cases in the main clause coming show to the pronoun looking is determined .

Reverse test method:

2.?

⁶ Current Uzbek literary language T.: Teacher, 1987. p. 187

- A) That I realized that he is human the ability infinite it is
- B) We so library let's build it, whole people next to happy and respectable let it be
- C) Dutor playing when I sit down, the string is broken went
- D) That's it happiness in class all students each other with very harmonious it is

(question options as follows to be possible)

1. Of the following answers which in one have follow speaking given a conjunction ?
2. In the main sentence filler explaining came followed joint spoken line define
3. The following of answers which in one that's it to the mold suitable not coming given a conjunction ?
4. The following of answers which in one determiner follow speaking given a conjunction ?
5. Well follow speaking a conjunction is given line define

Questions line that's it such as more by expanding you can also go .

So, from test technologies use in students to the topic about to the tests answer to give with one in line, they are also additional questions make up getting, literacy of degrees increase and of answers right or wrongness free analysis do it get enable gives From this method joint sentences from the topic except all mother language in their classes use in students makes sense thinking and creative activity to develop service does

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